

Partner Charter

Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure
– European Research Infrastructure
Consortium
(MIRRI-ERIC)

Purpose and applicability

The MIRRI-ERIC Partner Charter defines criteria for the participation of microbial domain biological resource centres (mBRCs), institutions providing microbial and/or genetic resources, services, training and expertise or participating in joint projects in the frame of the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI-ERIC). Altogether they are referred to as Partners.

The Partner Charter is binding for any Partner of MIRRI-ERIC and shall be agreed between the Partners and the national MIRRI-ERIC nodes.

Participation of a Partner in MIRRI-ERIC is non-exclusive and has no effect on any activity of a Partner outside of MIRRI-ERIC.

Any exceptions regarding the principles specified in this Partner Charter shall be addressed case by case.

The Partner Charter is applied together with the MIRRI-ERIC [Statutes](#) and Rules of Operation.

Principles for all Partners

- (1) Comply with the MIRRI-ERIC Policies specified in the Statutes and the Rules of Operations.
- (2) Provide information to the National MIRRI-ERIC Node on their activities to contribute to the annual report produced by the National Node. A template shall be provided.
- (3) Ensure to provide a high-quality offer of either microbial and/or genetic resources, services, training and/or expertise. Commit to implement a quality management system and/or quality assurance procedures following appropriate international standards suitable for the respective offer. In absence of official certification/accreditation, Partners shall make self-assessments based on checklists of minimal requirements and recommendations, reviewed by MIRRI-ERIC peers to support an adequate assessment of their compliance.
- (4) Agree to be, at any time, transparent to users. Partners will indicate which microbial and/or genetic resources, services, expertise, training, etc, are part of their contribution to MIRRI-ERIC's offer, and as such are following MIRRI-ERIC policies and rules.
- (5) Actively support activities to foster knowledge sharing, innovation and development arising from interaction of users and providers of MIRRI-ERIC.

- (6) Acknowledge the contribution of MIRRI-ERIC in any publication derived from projects supported by MIRRI-ERIC, according to the principles of good scientific practice.